

THE IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATION AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN IMPROVING EDUCATIONAL EFFICIENCY

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Abstract: the rapid development of science, technology, production and technology has opened up new prospects for the development of society in all spheres of its life. The centuries-old experience of mankind in building the state and society has led to the adoption of progressive approaches to the regulation of public relations based on new approaches. This article highlights the content of education, the concepts of pedagogical mastery. A study was also conducted on the importance of using innovative technologies in the educational process.

Keywords: education, pedagogy, methodology, innovations, innovative technologies.

ВАЖНОСТЬ ИННОВАЦИЙ И ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ПОВЫШЕНИИ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация: бурное развитие науки, техники, производства и техники открыло новые перспективы развития общества во всех сферах его жизни. Многовековой опыт человечества в построении государства и общества привел к принятию прогрессивных подходов к регулированию общественных отношений на основе новых подходов. В данной статье освещается содержание образования, понятия педагогического мастерства. Также было проведено исследование важности применения инновационных технологий в образовательном процессе.

Ключевые слова: Образование, Педагогика, методология, инновации, инновационные технологии.

INTRODUCTION

The development of Science and modern technologies is one of the priority tasks to be solved in the implementation of the socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in order for the Republic of Uzbekistan to enter the world markets and take a worthy place there, it is imperative to form an economic system in which the achievements of science are widely used, And in order to perfectly cope with such a responsible task, great importance has been attached to the rapid development of National Science and the personnel training system.

In the context of globalization, education occupies an important place in the comprehensive adult education of a person, in which perfection and the formation of qualities characteristic of a qualified specialist take place. Today's rapid period necessitates the creation of the necessary conditions for the armament of educators, including students, in the short term and with reasoned information, for the thorough assimilation by them of the foundations of various sciences. In accordance with the requirements of today's dynamically developing period, many urgent tasks arose due to the need for a new approach to the content and structure of education in the face of changing modern school education. Now in modern student – learning it is necessary not to use traditional methods of education, but to form and teach them the skills of obtaining independent knowledge and striving to improve the knowledge acquired.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

It is known that in the present era, a mentally intelligent, creatively gifted, inquisitive young people are a huge source of strength that moves the scientific technical progress of society, which

in the future will have to be integrated with the world community in all areas. In this regard, the search for young talented specialists, their correct orientation is one of the highest goals.

The power of any country is determined by its intellectual potential. And this directly depends on the quality of education. The system of general education that is being formed in our country contributes to the disclosure of the intellectual and moral potential of students, training in accordance with their abilities and capabilities, the education of gifted youth, contributes to the correct and informed choice of the path in the future, serves to ensure the adaptation of students to the changing requirements of the labor market and educational labor.

It is known to us that at present, changes are taking place in all material and spiritual spheres of our society, people are striving for specific goals and create important economic, spiritual conditions for themselves and serve to ensure sustainable development. One of the urgent problems of building a democratic society is the transformation of human thinking and spirituality. The emergence of new thinking, the understanding of the role and role of man in today's development has become an important factor in the development of society based on democratic principles. The main wealth of each state is a person. From this follows the conclusion that the main way to increase the wealth and power of the state is to form an intellectual culture in youth.

The purpose of modernization of education should be to ensure the progress of education and reflect in the system the needs, economic and social needs of society living in the XXI century, the needs of each individual and family. To create such a development system, it is necessary to carry out the following tasks:

- ensuring the right to full education by the state;
- ensuring the quality of modern education at all stages of the educational system;
- improvement of the legal and regulatory framework of education and identification and involvement of new resources of organizational and economic mechanisms;
- development and promotion of professional-innovative competence of pedagogical staff;
- wide introduction of the latest achievements of information and communication technologies into the educational system;
- development of a consortium between science, education and production;
- implementation of innovative educational technologies aimed at developing creative skills, intellectual qualities of young people in the system of continuing education, etc.

“Therefore, it is imperative that the teacher himself has professional and specialized skills, knows how to use new modern educational technologies that meet the requirements of the current period. The purpose of the pedagogical activity of any subject teacher, in particular, primary education teachers, is to make students know how to become a mature competent person, who will be in demand in modern society in the future, prepare them for their development as a creative thinking, aspiring person, and introduce innovative technologies[1, 24]”.

In essence, innovations are considered a dynamic system of introducing innovation into an attitude or process. Innovation as a system in itself represents the internal logic of an attitude or process, firstly, and, secondly, the consistent development of the innovation being entered over a certain period of time and the interaction it presents to the environment.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Innovative activity requires the acquisition of theoretical knowledge, practical skills and abilities based on the orientation of the mental, mental, physical strength of the educator to a specific goal, complementing practical activities with theoretical knowledge, developing the skills of cognition, design, communicative speech and organization.

"The sign of how much the human mind is used is determined by the volume of knowledge it possesses. The more a person uses his mind, the more his knowledge and the higher his social essence. In addition to him, man is also distinguished from other creatures by many secondary features. A person, in the process of reaching the goal, goes through a number of natural and artificial barriers. To overcome these obstacles, he applies several measures and measures"[2, 56].

As an element of the structure of the process of pedagogical innovation, the news carrier is characterized in terms of the unity of perception, assimilation and assessment of innovation, goal setting and goal achievement. The meaning of the word innovation comes from the English word "innovation", which means innovation and innovation. At the core of this innovation, it is necessary to understand a new order, a new habit, a new style and discovery. The concept of innovation is comprehensive, which implies the introduction of perfect, new, previously absent technologies into the production process, while innovation in the higher education system is understood as the modernization of management tasks and the educational process using modern information and communication tools to the management system of education, its functional sections, tasks, educational process.

Scientists of our country innovation by definition, it is:

- first, a certain set of information that has the idea of innovation (innovation is a hypothetical innovation in the form of a vision of information and in this sense);
- secondly, the idea of innovation in the process of making an appropriate decision (innovation in the form of a process of mastering it, introducing it, or an innovation that can be realized, realized);
- third, the result obtained or the innovation introduced.

"Innovative activity combines the fields of Science and production to allow them to increase their potential and is an instrument of scientific discoveries that can be introduced into practice as innovation[3]". The main aspects of the organization of innovative activities:

- development, implementation and implementation of innovations in innovative activities in the educational institution;
- a set of processes and actions aimed at fulfilling the necessary tasks in innovative activities in educational institutions;
- structures that ensure the improvement of the internal regulation of the system and the interaction between the systems of its elements.

Advanced pedagogical technologies and innovations do not enter the educational system on their own. This is a process that depends on the activity of the teacher and his motivation. Today, as a result of the emergence of ideas of a new scientific direction in the field of pedagogy – pedagogical innovation and renewal of the educational process, there is also the concept of a new direction in the pedagogical activity of the teacher "innovative activity of the teacher".

Today, the classification of innovations in the educational system is approved as follows:

- depending on the direction of activity (in the pedagogical process, in management);
- according to the classification of the changes introduced (radical, modified, combined);
- according to the scale of changes (local, modular, systemic);
- according to the source of origin (taken internally and externally for the same team).

Innovative education is such innovative educational technologies and programs in which the educator is the result of innovative activity, and those who teach are the creators of innovative ideas, and an innovative project is a combination of technical, organizational, planned, and calculation – financial documents necessary for the implementation of project goals.

The main tasks of applying advanced pedagogical and information technologies to the educational system, improving the material technical base of educational institutions are as follows:

- * creation of a material and technical base necessary for the implementation of new information technologies in the educational process;
- * creation and application of new informatized educational technologies for the educational process;
- * formation of students ' knowledge and skills in the field of modern information and communication technologies;
- * improving the effectiveness of the educational training and training process.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the fundamental changes taking place in the educational process in our country require the acceleration of the educational sphere in each educational institution, while the path to the introduction of innovation is always a complex and long process. It is safe to say that pedagogical technology and innovative technologies remain the main source of innovation in education.

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